

TREASoURcE

D9.2 Joint CCRI deliverable 1

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
BT	Business Tampere
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CE	Circular Economy
CLIC	CLIC Innovation Ltd
CSS	Circular Systemic Solution
D	Deliverable report
DMP	Data Management Plan
ECO	ECO STOR AS
EKOF	Ekokumppanit Oy (EcoFellows)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
Frstad	Fredrikstad kommune
FVH	Forum Virium Helsinki Oy
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	GreenDelta GMBH
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KVC	Key value chain
KVC-DEMO	Key value chain demonstration
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners
PF	Polyfuels Group AB (Previously known as Green Ideas Group GIG)
SDU	Syddansk Universitet
SE	Stakeholder engagement
SE-DEMO	Stakeholder engagement demonstration
SINTEF	SINTEF AS / SINTEF Energy
TalTech	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool
TARTU	Tartu Linn (Tartu City)
TLN	Tallinna Linn (City of Tallinn)
VIKEN	Viken Fylkeskommune
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the activities of the TREASoURcE project relating to the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) and the Thematic Working Groups (TWG) as well as collaboration established with other CCRI-projects, and CCRI Pilots and Fellows. It also summarises policy recommendation related work done. This is the first of three deliverables in this topic, the deliverable is always updated for each of the project periods (period 1 M1-M18; period 2 M19-M36; period 3 M37-M48).

TREASoURcE has been actively involved in the CCRI activities organised by the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO) throughout its first period. In total, TREASoURcE was represented in 50+ CCRI related events and occasions where it held presentations or otherwise represented the project (e.g. with a poster). TREASoURcE held a collaboration session with its sister CCRI projects on 1.12.2022, where the different projects were introduced, possible collaboration points identified and connections between the key personnel made. In total, TREASoURcE has collaborated with 20+ projects. TREASoURcE has also established collaborations with the following CCRI Pilots and Fellows: Helsinki-Uusimaa Circular Valley and Helsinki-Uusimaa region (Finland), Tampere region (Finland), and city of Berlin (Germany), Asker municipality (Norway), and Møre og Romsdal county (Norway). In addition, several other cities, municipalities and regions and their local stakeholders have been collaborated with outside the CCRI network, for example Tartu (Estonia), Tallinn (Estonia), Riga (Latvia), Kaunas (Lithuania), Warsaw (Poland), Lempäälä (Finland), Turku (Finland), Salo (Finland), Forssa (Finland), Satakunta region (Finland), Jyväskylä region (Finland), Soikamo (Finland), Häme region (Finland), and from Norway: Kongsberg, Flå, Indre Østfold, Rakkestad, Spydeberg, Marker, Nordre Follo, Lier, Ringebu, Vestby, Drammen, Nittedal, Bærum, Aurskog-Høland, and Nannestad.

TREASoURcE has been active in three Thematic Working Groups (TWG) hosted by the CCRI-CSO: circular resource management, industrial symbiosis, and circular economy in industries, as well as circular bioeconomy. Main activities include the participation in the TWG sessions, sharing actively the expected outputs and giving project related presentations. In Period 2, TREASoURcE will continue to actively participate in the CCRI and TWG activities.

The work towards policy recommendations is on-going. In TREASoURcE work package (WP) 1 and T1.3 is focusing on legislation review. The work is currently in progress and carrying out the legislative review, which includes a review of relevant value chain related EU-level regulations, directives as well as standards. The review is finalised during 2023, and the next steps in 2024 focus on validating the identified policy related barriers with stakeholders. The work will lead towards policy recommendations. In Work Package 2, part of the stakeholder engagement demonstrations is the circular economy (CE) wise procurement activities. The policy recommendations will be done in collaboration with WP1 and WP2 as well as the KVC WPs (WP3-WP5). WP2 will also engage in local/regional policy implementation to advance CE. Policy recommendations have been developed relating to bio-based side and waste streams and repurposing of end-of-life electric vehicle batteries as stationary energy systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable outlines the activities of the TREASoURcE project relating to the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) and the Thematic Working Groups (TWG) as well as collaboration established with other CCRI-projects, and CCRI Pilots and Fellows. It also summarises policy recommendation related work done. This is the first of three deliverables in this topic, the deliverable is always updated for each of the project periods (period 1 M1-M18; period 2 M19-M36; period 3 M37-M48).

The CCRI is an initiative of the European Commission, launched by the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation as part of the EU Circular Economy Action Plan 2020. It contributes to the policy objectives of the EU Green Deal, including the 2050 climate neutrality target, and the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. The CCRI is funded by Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe, the EU's research, and innovation framework programmes. TREASoURcE has received funding from the Horizon Europe programme. The aim of the initiative is to combine knowledge sharing, technical and financial support, the initiative assists stakeholders across Europe's cities and regions, including regional and local authorities, industry representatives, research and technology organisations and civil society (European Commission, 2023).

The CCRI-projects are part of the multi-stakeholder collaboration and support scheme. The aim of the CCRI-projects is to demonstrate circular systemic solutions (CSS) and to test circular business and governance models. TREASoURcE is focusing on developing systemic circular solutions that are a combination of the key value chain demonstrations (KVC-DEMOS, technical part of the project) and stakeholder engagement demonstrations (SE-DEMOS). We actively seek to share as openly as possible the work, methodologies, learnings, and results of our project. All possible outputs will be uploaded to the TREASoURcE Replication Handbook. It is a central platform for the project to upload all possible exploitable and replicable results to be accessible to all.

2. CCRI collaboration

2.1. Collaboration with CCRI, CCRI-CSO, CCRI Projects, CCRI Pilots and Fellows

TREASoURcE has been actively involved in the CCRI activities organised by the CCRI-CSO throughout its first period. In total, TREASoURcE was represented in several different CCRI hosted events and occasions where it held presentations or otherwise represented the project (e.g., with a poster). TREASoURcE also organised many events, where CCRI has been introduced either by the TREASoURcE personnel or CCRI or CCRI-CSO representatives.

TREASoURcE held a collaboration session with its sister CCRI projects on 1.12.2022, where the different projects were introduced, possible collaboration points identified and connections between the key personnel made. TREASoURcE held the session with the following CCRI projects: Agro2Circular, HOOP, FRONTSH1P, and SYSCHEMIQ.

TREASoURcE has also established active collaborations with the following CCRI Pilots and Fellows: Helsinki-Uusimaa Circular Valley and Helsinki-Uusimaa region (Finland), Tampere region (Finland), and city of Berlin (Germany), Asker municipality (Norway), and Møre og Romsdal county (Norway). We have organised several events where the Pilot and Fellows have been invited to and many times have held presentations.

List of main CCRI activities in Period 1 (P1), TWG participation reported in the next chapter:

- Completion of CCRI-CSO cooperation questionnaire on TREASoURcE contributions, activities, and outcomes throughout P1.
- CCRI and CCRI-CSO introduction presentation in the TREASoURcE project kick-off *meeting* 18.8.2022 (Annika Eskusson, Jan Wynarski)
- 24.8.2022 CCRI-CSO cooperation *meeting* with CCRI-CSO and TREASoURcE CCRI-team (=Coordinator Anna T-L and communication and dissemination manager Kaisa Simola)
- CCRI-CSO Coordination and support *workshop* in Brussels, Belgium 19.10.2022. Participation from Anna T-L and Kaisa Simola.
- Collaboration session *workshop* with 4 other CCRI-projects at the 2nd Consortium Meeting of TREASoURcE on 1.12.2022: Agro2Circular, HOOP, FRONTSH1P, SYSCHEMIQ.
- TREASoURcE presentation and tips for building proposals presented at the CCRI-CSO *webinar* on Horizon Europe topics for CE at local and regional scale on 15.12.2022 by the Coordinator. Presentation: *Introduction to CCRI-project TREASoURcE & roles of cities and regions in the project.*
- TREASoURcE presentation at the World Circular Economy Forum *event* in Helsinki on 1.6.2023 at the CCRI accelerator session by Anna T-L.
- Presentation of the CCRI and CCRI-CSO in the TREASoURcE Warsaw (Poland) replication *workshop* 20.6.2023 (by CCRI-CSO representative Jan Wynarski)
- Participation in CCRI Multi-Stakeholder Dialogue on “What R&I gaps must be bridged to boost circular economy implementation in cities and regions from a governance perspective?” *meeting*, 20.6.2023 (Henrik Brynthe Lund, SINTEF)
- CCRI Project online *workshop*: Unleashing the potential of the CCRI Demonstration Projects through collaboration. 22.9.2023, online. Anna T-L held a presentation about TREASoURcE and its circular systemic solutions.
- CCRI General Conference 8.11.2023, Brussels. Anna T-L and Pirkko Eteläaho participated F2F.
- CCRI TWG Workshops, 9.11.2023, Brussels. Participation in sessions: Circular Resources Management (Anna T-L, Pirkko Eteläaho); Circular Bioeconomy (Anna T-L); Industrial symbiosis and circular industries (Pirkko E.)

2.2. Thematic Working Groups

TREASoURcE has been active in three Thematic Working Groups hosted by the CCRI Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO): circular resource management, industrial symbiosis and circular economy in industries, as well as circular bioeconomy. The following persons have been included in the TWGs:

- *Bioeconomy*: Anna T-L, Kaisa Simola, Riina Kärki (MTK, Riina leads the KVC work package WP5 bio-based side and waste streams)
- *Circular Resource Management*: Anna T-L, Kaisa Simola, Pirkko Eteläaho (from BT, Pirkko leads the circular business, exploitation, and funding related matters)
- *Industrial symbiosis and CE in industries*: Anna T-L, Kaisa Simola, Tiina Laiho (CLIC, Tiina leads the work and demonstrations related to symbiotic B2B partnerships)

In Period 1, main activities include the participation in the Thematic Working Group sessions, sharing actively the expected outputs and giving project related presentations. In Period 2, TREASoURcE will continue to actively participate the CCRI and TWG activities.

The participation in the following TWG meetings:

- 19.10.2022 Circular Resource Management (as part of the first CCRI Coordination and Support Workshop in Brussels)
- 7.3.2023 Circular Resource Management
- 7.3.2023 Industrial Symbiosis
- 8.3.2023 and 7.6.2023 Circular Bioeconomy
- 22.6.2023 CCRI 5th Webinar | Navigating the funding landscape
- 12.9.2023 CCRI-TWG IS subgroup "Strategies" workshop
- 3.10.2023 CCRI-TWG IS subgroup "Mapping & matchmaking " workshop
- 6.10.2023 CCRI-TWG IS subgroup "Capacity building " workshop, presentation on Tampere region and TREASoURcE project activities by Pirkko E.
- 24.10.2023 CCRI-TWG IS subgroup "Strategies" workshop
- 9.11.2023 CCRI TWG Circular Resource Management
- 9.11.2023 CCRI TWG Circular bioeconomy
- 9.11.2023 CCRI TWG Industrial symbiosis and circular industry

3. Collaboration with other projects, networks, and regions

In total, TREASoURcE has collaborated with 20+ projects, 18 networks and 14+ regions/cities/municipalities.

Other projects:

- **BIOTRANSFORM**: Co-operation meeting 27.3.23 (MTK: Kärki and Berglund, EKOF: Koivisto, Frstad: Langvik); Working Group Session 10.10.23 (MTK: Kärki)
- Collaboration with the Norwegian nationally funded project **SafeBESS** through organization of a common webinar (18th of January, 2024) and workshop
- **Just food** co-operation meeting 23.3.23 (MTK: Kärki and Berglund)
- **Enchant**: project meeting 26th September (Viken, WP2)
- **FER-PLAY**: Towards the co-creation of better regulation frameworks for alternative fertilisers, meeting #1 18.9.23 (MTK: Berglund); Regulatory challenges and opportunities for various fertilising products, meeting #2 28.9.2023 (MTK: Berglund); Working group 7.11.23 (MTK: Kärki and Berglund)
- **HOOP** (collaboration emails and attendance in Webinar: Project Development Assistance for the Circular Economy 24.5.23)
- **MuKi**: Meeting 28.9.22 (MTK, EKOF); Meeting 7.12.2022 (MTK, EKOF); Meeting 13.2.2023 (MTK, EKOF); Workshop 20.4.2023 (MTK); Co-organized simultaneous regional sister workshops (Agriculture plastic related) 31.10.2023 (CLIC, MTK, EKOF, VTT, BF)
- **eMuovi**: eMuovi -project steering group meeting 19.12.2022 (MTK); Meeting 30.1.2023 (MTK); Meeting 13.2.2023 (MTK, EKOF); Meeting 13.4.2023 (MTK); eMuovi -project steering group meeting 17.4.2023 (MTK); eMuovi -project steering group meeting 5.9.2023 (MTK)
- **PlastLife** co-operation meeting 8.12.2023 participants MTK, VTT, EKOF
- **KieMaRa**: Participation to workshop: 24.1.2023 (MTK: Berglund, EKOF: Koivisto); Speech (MTK: Kärki) at the webinar "Agricultural circular economy solutions in Häme" 24.10.23. Introducing TREASoURcE and KiertoaSuomesta.fi
- **AgroEko**: Meeting dates: 15.12.2022 (EKOF: Koivisto, MTK: Kärki & Berglund); Co-organized Biogas Seminar for Mänttä-Vilppula (EKOF: Koivisto, MTK: Berglund)
- **CEGO** – Circular Economy Goes East and West -project (attending several events 2022-2023) (MTK, CLIC)
- **KIPSI** -project (co-organizer a Field day in Kokemäki, Finland 9.10.2023)
- **Muutosvoimaa tulevaan** -project (several meetings and co-operaton e.g., in Field day Kokemäki 9.10.2023)
- **Satotason nosto Länsi-Suomessa** -project / ProAgria Länsi-Suomi (co-organizer in Kokemäki field day)
- **FinBaltRecycling** (several meetings 2023 MTK, EKOF)
- **IFDEA** -project – The rulebook for a fair data economy in agriculture (Several meetings 2022-23: MTK)
- Co-operation with **Tuotto** project (WP5)
- Co-operation with **TaloMaalta** -project (WP5)
- Co-operation with **Luontoarvot.fi** -project (WP5)
- **KIERTOTRE**-project (BT), rigid plastics collection pilot (companies) Q4/2023, synergies with TREASoURcE rigid plastics collection pilot (consumers) (WP2, WP3, WP6)

Other networks and associations:

- **Biomass Atlas** (WP5)
- Co-operation with **Finnish Biocycle and Biogas Association** (WP5)
- Co-operation with **ProAgria** (WP5)
- **ECO3** (WP3, WP5, WP6)
- **Circular Economy Green Deal Finland** (several meetings 2022-2023) (MTK, Kärki, BT, Ete-läaho)
- **Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment** (Finland)
- **Gaia-X Finland** – Circular Economy domain working group MTK unions (WP5)
- **Circular Economy Finland** (KiSu)
- **European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform**
 - Circular Bioeconomy Value Chains Insights and Best Practices 5.10.22 (MTK: Kärki)
 - Circular Procurement: Catalyst for Biodiversity and Climate Resilience 20.10.2023 (MTK: Berglund)
- **World Circular Economy Forum** (WP8, WP9)
 - Accelerator session in Helsinki for WCEF 2024
- **Nordic Circular Hotspot** (CLIC, WP8)
- **Finnish Plastic Industries Federation** (WP3)
- **Climate network Pirkanmaa** (WP5)
- **Tampere Region Climate Partner Network** (BT, all WP's)
- **Tampere Region Circular Economy and Cleantech Ecosystem** (BT, all WP's)
- **Tampere Region Intelligent Machines And Automation Ecosystem** (BT, WP4 & WP6)
- **Tampere Region Automotive Ecosystem** (BT, WP4 & WP6)
- **Sustainable Industry X** (SIX) network (BT, WP4 & WP6)
- **Biogass Oslofjord** (WP5)
- **Klimapartnere** (All WPs)
- **Klimasmart Landbruk** (WP5)
- **Partnerskap for næring** (WP2)
- **Norges Bondelag** (WP5)
- **KS Sirkulærøkonominettverk** (all WPs)

In addition, several other cities, municipalities and regions and their local stakeholders have been collaborated with outside the CCRI network:

- Tartu (Estonia)
- Tallinn (Estonia)
- Riga (Latvia)
- Kaunas (Lithuania)
- Warsaw (Poland)
- Lempäälä (Finland)
- Turku (Finland)
- Salo (Finland)
- Forssa (Finland)
- Satakunta region (Finland)
- Jyväskylä region (Finland)
- Sotkamo (Finland)
- Häme region (Finland)
- Kongsberg (Norway)
- Flå (Norway)
- Indre Østfold (Norway)
- Rakkestad (Norway)
- Spydeberg (Norway)
- Marker (Norway)
- Nordre Follo (Norway)
- Lier (Norway)
- Ringerike (Norway)
- Vestby (Norway)
- Drammen (Norway)
- Nittedal (Norway)
- Bærum (Norway)
- Aurskog-Høland (Norway)
- Nannestad (Norway)

4. Policy recommendations

In TREASoURcE, all project activities are considered to contribute to data gathering or generation, new knowledge, identification of gaps and barriers and development of possible solutions and ideas to overcome identified gaps and barriers. Policy recommendations are generated on different levels when relevant – local, regional, national and EU level.

In TREASoURcE work package WP1 and *T1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework* is focusing on legislation review. As part of *T1.4 (State-of-the-art for technologies, best practices, and circular business models in Europe)* and *T1.3*, three Master's Theses were done on each of the value chain, where a thorough desktop study was done on the state-of-the-art analysis of the technologies and identified barriers. The literature review formed a baseline that was used in interviews with value chain actors to find barriers and opportunities for CE for each of the value chain. The work in *T1.3* has been continued based on the theses and work done in *T4.1 Challenges & barriers for battery 2nd life* and *WP5 KVC-DEMOS: Circular biobased side and waste streams for biogas and fertilizers*. In *T1.3*, a thorough review has been completed which included a review of relevant value chain related EU-level regulations, directives as well as standards. The next steps in 2024 focus on validating the identified policy related barriers with stakeholders. These will be reported in the *D1.3 Legislative and regulatory framework for target value chains*. The work will lead towards policy recommendations.

In Work Package 2, part of the stakeholder engagement demonstrations is the CE wise procurement activities. The policy recommendations will be done in collaboration with WP1 and WP2 as well as the KVC WPs (WP3-WP5). WP2 will also engage in local/regional policy implementation to advance CE.

In Period 1, TREASoURcE has generated some policy recommendations already:

- D1.1 identified key takeaways for policymakers for developing strategies, roadmaps and action plans to promote circular economy. The findings of the report are also presented in a scientific publication, currently under review. (WP1)
- Taken part in developing policy recommendations for the regional plans for Viken on the topics of "*Mobility and Land use*", "*Competence and Value Creation*", and "*Increased quality of life, participation, and equity*" (WP2)
- To support repurposing of end-of-life vehicles to stationary energy storage applications, D1.4 and a scientific publication have been made with recommendations. (WP4, WP1)
- Preparations for a policy recommendation on supporting systemic transition to circularity regarding the bio-based side and waste streams in Finland are made, publication expected in Period 2. (WP1, WP5)

The work towards further policy recommendations is on-going and will be published in upcoming periods.

5. REFERENCES

European Commission. (2023). *Circular Cities and Regions Initiative*. Retrieved from <https://circular-cities-and-regions.ec.europa.eu/about>